

Industry Case Study - English Version

Início do bloqueio: Consent Block

Presentation **Study on the Use of Programming Assistants Based on Artificial Intelligence**

This study is part of the postgraduate research conducted by master student Lucas Lucio (Federal Technological University of Paraná - UTFPR) and doctoral student Nicole Davila (Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul - UFRGS), with guidance from professors Igor Wiese and André Kawamoto (both from UTFPR).

Summary:

This is an 11-minute survey of their experiences using Artificial Intelligence (AI) based programming assistants such as GitHub Copilot and ChatGPT. You can participate in a raffle to win 1 of 2 R\$50.00 IFood gift cards at the end of the survey.

Goal:

The aim of the study is to understand the use of AI-based programming assistants during the software development process in the context of your company.

Procedure:

This is an 11-minute quiz about your experiences using AI-based programming assistants like GitHub Copilot and ChatGPT. If you agree to participate in this study, you will be asked questions about your experiences and challenges using these tools, information about your experiences with software development, and demographic information. Your participation is not mandatory, and at any time, you may withdraw from participating and withdraw your consent, which will not entail prejudice.

Questions and contact information:

If you have any questions about this study, please feel free to contact the study researchers:

- Lucas Lúcio - UTFPR - lucas.1999@alunos.utfpr.edu.br
- Nicole Davila - UFRGS - ncdavila@inf.ufrgs.br
- Igor Wiese - UTFPR - igor@utfpr.edu.br
- Andre Kawamoto - UTFPR - kawamoto@utfpr.edu.br

If you have further questions, require additional information, or withdraw your participation, please contact one of the researchers via email using the contact information listed above.

Voluntary Participation:

Your participation in this research is voluntary, and there will be no cost to you if you participate in this study. You may discontinue participation at any time during the survey activity.

Benefits:

There may be no personal benefit from your participation in the study, but your participation will

be valuable in building knowledge in the area of software engineering. You can participate in a raffle to win 1 of 2 R\$50.00 IFood gift cards at the end of the survey.

Confidentiality:

I understand that all information is confidential. I will not be identified personally. I agree to complete the questionnaire for research purposes and that data derived from this anonymous survey may be published in journals, conferences, and blog posts.

By clicking the button below, I freely agree and acknowledge my rights as a voluntary research participant as described above and consent to researchers using my information for research in the abovementioned areas.

Q1 If you agree to participate in this research, proceed with the survey.

- I have read and understood the above information. (1)

Fim do bloco: Consent Block

Início do bloqueio: Basic Information Block

Q2 What is your academic background in software development?

- Bachelor degree in Computer Science (1)
- Bachelor degree in Informatics (2)
- Bachelor degree in Computer Engineering (3)
- Bachelor degree in Software Engineering (4)
- Information systems (5)
- Information Technology (6)
- Technology in Systems Analysis and Development (7)
- I have no academic background in software development (8)
- Other: (9) _____
-

Q3 How many years of professional software development experience do you have?
Consider time at the current company and previous professional experiences. If you have less than 1 year of experience, indicate 0 in the field below.

Q4 What is your gender?

- Woman (1)
- Man (2)
- Transgender (3)
- Non-binary/non-conforming (4)
- Prefer not to respond (5)

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Description_Q5 **Software Development Team**: Consider all the professionals who work in your group/team/work team to execute projects or maintain existing software systems.

Q5 Which of the following cases is your software development team currently most involved in?

- I work mainly with the legacy system of the company. (1)
 - I dedicate my time mainly to the development of new applications with the newest technologies in the industry. (2)
 - I balance my work between the legacy system and the development of new applications. (3)
-

Q6 What programming languages do you work with at the company??

You can select more than one option.

- I do not work with programming (1)
 - Java (2)
 - JavaScript (3)
 - PHP (4)
 - Python (5)
 - TypeScript (6)
 - Uniface (7)
 - Other (8) _____
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Description_Q7 **Code Review**: Code review is a software quality assurance activity with the following characteristics:

- (i) the changed code is reviewed by one or more humans, at least one of which humans is not the author of the code change;
 - (ii) the review is mainly performed by visualizing and reading the source code;
 - (iii) the humans who perform the review, excluding the author, are called "reviewers".
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Q7 In the context of your software development team, is or has a code review been performed?

- Code reviews are currently performed on all products under the team's responsibility. (1)
- Code reviews are currently performed, but only for some of the products under the team's responsibility. (2)
- Code reviews have been done in the past, but it is no longer an adopted practice within the team. (3)
- Code reviews have been done in the past and have been deliberately discontinued across the team. (4)
- Code review was never adopted in the team. (5)

Fim do bloco: Basic Information Block

Início do bloqueio: Block on the Use of AI-Based Tools

Q8 Have you used an AI-based programming assistant at your job in the past 12 months?*

Examples of AI-based programming assistants: ChatGPT, GitHub Copilot, Bing Chat, Bard, etc.

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

*Pular para: Fim do bloco Se Have you used an AI-based programming assistant at your job in the past 12 months?** Examples of A... = No

Q9 Describe types of situations where you are most successful using AI-based programming assistants in your work.

Q10 How do you perceive the importance of using AI-based programming assistants in the following situations?

	Very important (1)	Important (2)	Neutral (3)	Slightly important (4)	Not important (5)	I don't know/ Prefer not to answer (6)
To finish my programming tasks more quickly. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To have autocomplete or reduce typing effort. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To reduce online searches for specific code snippets, programming syntax, or API calls I know but can not remember. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To find better alternatives or starting points for writing a solution to a problem I'm facing. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To find an edge case for my code that I didn't consider. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To collaborate with someone else who	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

writes code
in a
programming
language
other than
mine. (6)

To check for
syntax issues
in my code.
(7)

To review if
someone
else's code
has syntax
issues. (8)

Q11 Which of the following tools have you worked with in the past 12 months??
Check all applicable options.

Amazon CodeWhisperer (1)

Bard (2)

Bing Chat (3)

Web search engine (Google, Bing, etc) (4)

ChatGPT (5)

GitHub Copilot (6)

Stack Overflow (7)

Others (8) _____

Q12 How do you estimate how often you use the tools below in a workweek?

Exibir esta opção:
 If Which of the following tools have you worked with in the past 12 months?? Check all applicable op... = Others

	Very frequent (every day) (1)	Frequent (4 to 3 days a week) (2)	Occasionally (2 or 1 days a week) (3)	Rarely (I don't use it for a few weeks) (4)	I already tried to use the tool, but I abandoned it (5)	Never/I don't know about this tool (6)
Amazon CodeWhisperer (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bard (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Bing Chat (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Web search engine (Google, Bing, etc) (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
ChatGPT (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
GitHub Copilot (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Stack Overflow (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Exibir esta opção: If Which of the following tools have you worked with in the past 12 months?? Check all applicable op... = Others	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Others (8)						

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Q13 Estimate how often you use AI-based programming assistants (e.g., ChatGPT, GitHub Copilot, etc) in the following situations in a workweek.

	Very frequent (every day) (1)	Frequent (4 to 3 days a week) (2)	Occasionally (2 or 1 days a week) (3)	Rarely (I don't use it for a few weeks) (4)	Never (5)
To finish my programming tasks more quickly. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To have autocomplete or reduce typing effort. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To reduce online searches for specific code snippets, programming syntax, or API calls I know but can not remember. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To find better alternatives or starting points for writing a solution to a problem I'm facing. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To find an edge case for my code that I didn't consider. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To collaborate with someone else who writes code in a	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

programming language other than mine. (6)

To check for syntax issues in my code. (7)

To review if someone else's code has syntax issues. (8)

<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="radio"/>				

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Q14 Describe one or more examples of difficulties or problems you have faced in using AI-based programming assistants in your work.

Q15 Considering your experience using AI-based programming assistants, estimate how often you experience the following scenarios per week.

	Very frequent (every day) (1)	Frequent (4 to 3 days a week) (2)	Occasionally (2 or 1 days a week) (3)	Rarely (I don't use it for a few weeks) (4)	Never (5)
I find it difficult to express my intent or requirements through natural language for the tool. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find it difficult to judge that the suggestion is correct and error-free. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I don't know what part of my code or comments the tool is using to make suggestions. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find it difficult to control the tool to generate code that I find useful. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I rely on tools to write code for me. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q16 Describe one or more examples of strategies you've used to get an AI-based programming assistant to generate the best answers for you.

Attention Check Please select Strongly Agree to indicate that you are paying attention to this question.

- Strongly Agree (1)
- Agree (6)
- Neutral (7)
- Disagree (8)
- Strongly disagree (9)

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Fim do bloco: Block on the Use of AI-Based Tools

Início do bloqueio: Block on Not Using AI-Based Tools

Q17 How much each of the following factors influences your decision **not to use** AI-based programming assistants (e.g., ChatGPT, GitHub Copilot, etc)?
 On a scale of 1 to 5, consider that 5 represents a very high influence and 1 represents no influence.

	5 (1)	4 (2)	3 (3)	2 (4)	1 (5)
I do not find the suggestions helpful. (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
The suggestions are very complex. (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
I can't understand the tool's suggestions. (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
I write and use proprietary code that the tool does not cover. (4)	<input type="radio"/>				
I don't want to use open source code. (5)	<input type="radio"/>				
I want to avoid potential intellectual property (IP) infringement. (6)	<input type="radio"/>				
Suggestions take a lot of time to debug or modify. (7)	<input type="radio"/>				
It is difficult to control the tool to get the desired output. (8)	<input type="radio"/>				

The suggestions do not meet the functional or non-functional (eg security, performance) requirements needed. (9)

Q18 Are there any other important reasons for you not to use an AI-based programming assistant? If yes, please describe these reasons.

Fim do bloco: Block on Not Using AI-Based Tools

Início do bloqueio: Q&A Block

Exibir esta pergunta:

If Have you used an AI-based programming assistant at your job in the past 12 months? Examples of A... = Yes*

Q19 Considering your current work, estimate how often you use Q&A communities, for instance, Stack Overflow.

- Always. Q&A Communities are my go-to source when I need help with a problem, question, or difficulty at work. (1)
- Often. I use Q&A communities as often as I use other tools (e.g., ChatGPT, GitHub Copilot, web browser, etc). (2)
- Sometimes when I can't get help with other tools (e.g., ChatGPT, GitHub Copilot, web browser, etc). (3)
- Rarely. It's common to get the desired answer in other tools (e.g., ChatGPT, GitHub Copilot, web browser, etc) and I don't need to use Q&A communities. (4)
- Never, I'm not using Q&A communities. (5)
- I have never used Q&A communities. (6)

Exibir esta pergunta:

If Have you used an AI-based programming assistant at your job in the past 12 months? Examples of A... = Yes*

Q20 How do you see your relationship with Q&A communities, such as Stack Overflow, after the emergence of tools like ChatGPT and GitHub Copilot?

- I do not perceive any change. I continue to use Q&A communities just as often. (1)
- I notice a change, but not a significant one. I still use Q&A communities even though I also use other tools. (2)
- I notice a change, but I do not know how to estimate if the frequency of use has changed. (3)
- I notice a significant change, with a reduction in the frequency that I use Q&A communities. (4)
- I notice a change, because today I no longer use Questions & Answers communities. (5)
- I have never used Q&A communities. (6)

Fim do bloco: Q&A Block

Início do bloqueio: Final Block

Q21 Do you have any other comments about your experience with programming assistants or problems you encountered answering this survey?

Q22 Can we contact you via email for further questions about our research?

Sim (1)

Não (2)

Exibir esta pergunta:

If Can we contact you via email for further questions about our research? = Sim

Q23 If you are available to contribute to our research, please leave your email address:

Fim do bloco: Final Block
